

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP3 - Development of the Virtual Ecosystem
for Research Activation (VERA)

VERA Core Design and Development

date 29.12.2021

This deliverable is licenced under
a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence.

COESO has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014-2020)
SwafS-27-2020 - Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation, under Grant Agreement No.101006325

The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the COESO consortium and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Deliverable 3.2

VERA Core Design and Development

Grant Agreement number	: 101006325
Project acronym	: COESO
Project title	: Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues
Funding Scheme	: H2020-EU.5. - SCIENCE WITH AND FOR SOCIETY
Topic	: SwafS-27-2020 - Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation
Project's coordinator Organization	: EHESS-OpenEdition
E-mail address	: pierre.mounier@openedition.org , alessia.smaniotto@openedition.org
Website	: https://coeso.hypotheses.org
WP and tasks contributing	: WP3 (Task 3.2)
WP leader	: Net7
Task leader	: Net7
Dissemination level	: PU
Due date	: 31/12/2021
Delivery date	: 29/12/2021
Authors	: Luca De Santis (Net7), Giulio Andreini (Net7), William J Costello (Net7), Tiziana Lombardo (Net7),
Contributors	: Francisco Sanz García (Ibercivis)
Reviewers	: Pierre Mounier (EHESS), Jessica Pidoux (FNSP-CEE)

Contents

Executive Summary	4
Introduction	4
User research process in VERA	6
VERA: main functionalities	8
VERA architecture	9
Technologies	14
VERA integration	16
VERA in the context of OPERAS	16
Integration with EU-Citizen.Science	20
Conclusions	21

I. Executive Summary

The aim of this document is to describe the state of the art of the VERA Core¹ development (alpha version).

VERA stands for “Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation”, a collaboration platform designed to manage SSH Citizen Science projects to be done in partnerships between scientific institutions and engaged stakeholders. It is the technological outcome of COESO and the present document describes the alpha version of it, which at the time of this deliverable’s release, has been developed and installed in the internal systems of Net7.

This document is structured in seven main sections, describing:

1. the presentation of VERA, its purposes and its role in the context of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure (chapter II)
2. the on-going user research work for defining the design of the platform (chapter III)
3. the main functionalities of VERA (chapter IV)
4. its technical architecture (chapter V)
5. the main technologies chosen for its development (chapter VI)
6. the path towards the integration of VERA with OPERAS’ services, as well as with the EU-Citizen.Science platform (chapter VII)
7. conclusions.

This document is the main output of task 3.2 (VERA core system design and development). The current version has been released at Month 12 (December 2021) and describes the alpha version of VERA.

The roadplan for the complete implementation of the platform includes these main steps: at M24 (December 2022) the beta version of VERA will be released together with the dashboard and the matchmaking interface (task 3.3): an updated version of this deliverable will be also published. One month later the EU-Citizen.science connector will be available (task 3.6). Finally, at Month 30 (May 2023) the VERA development will be completed, with the integration of collaboration tools and services (task 3.4) and the availability of the VERA Widget (task 3.5), a Wordpress plug-in to promote VERA projects on external websites.

II. Introduction

The goal of VERA is to provide a powerful but easy to use collaboration platform, where citizen science projects can take shape and successfully be carried out. Users will participate together in these projects, each one with specific goals, purposes, topics and requirements. VERA will provide users with the collaborative functionalities they need to carry out the initiatives, through services either internal or, mainly, external to COESO.

VERA in fact will not directly provide project management tools; we assume that the actual collaboration (e.g. writing on a shared document, working on a budget by using a spreadsheet,

¹ From now on, we simply refer to the platform as “VERA”.

communicating with the outside world via social media,...) happens through the use of existing, widely used external services, that will be integrated in VERA.

VERA is developed with a long-term perspective, since it will become one of the central services offered by the **OPERAS Research Infrastructure** (<https://www.operas-eu.org/>), whose goal is to support open scholarly communication in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area. Its mission is to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH.

OPERAS is developing a catalog of different scholarly communication services², a set of specialized web platforms to address the specific needs of the SSH research community. Amongst them there are: the **Discovery Service** GoTriple (<https://gotriple.eu/>), a multilingual discovery platform, that provides a single access point to research data in the context of SSH, in particular publications, datasets, projects and researcher profiles; the **Certification Service**, provided through DOAB (<https://doabooks.org/>), which offers a single access point to the list of certified peer reviewed SSH monographs available in Open Access; the **Metrics Service**, which collects usage and impact metrics related to SSH Open Access monographs from many different sources; the **Publishing Service Portal**, which collects the publishing and scholarly communication services offered by OPERAS members; the **Research for Society Service**, based on the Hypotheses blogging platform (<https://hypotheses.org/>), which aims to stimulate on-going discussions and reflections between SSH researchers and the society at large.

In this context, VERA will upgrade the Research for Society Service of OPERAS, providing an answer to a very specific need, that is the possibility for engaged stakeholders to create and manage participatory research projects in the SSH domain. All its functionalities are therefore designed by considering the needs, the expectations, the collaboration dynamics of this specific kind of citizen science initiatives and of the people who are involved in them.

Albeit OPERAS is not an e-infrastructure, it is undeniable that technology is a fundamental asset in the realization of its mission: because of that it is fundamental, when designing a new software system for an OPERAS project, to see it as a component of a larger ecosystem, made of all OPERAS “high level” services (e.g. Discovery, Metrics, Certification, ...) but also of its single application components, that might be reused or exploited in the new development: we can define this goal as the “valorisation principle”.

VERA is the first main OPERAS service that is developed by considering the “valorisation principle” from its early design. This is pursued with a twofold approach: on the one hand by exploiting features of the existing OPERAS services in its development, and on the other by making some of VERA’s own functionalities as versatile as possible and open for reuse in other OPERAS implementations. The technical details of this approach are described in the chapters that follow.

As said, VERA has been currently released in alpha version: while the technological foundations have been defined and implemented, as described herein, the actual collaboration dynamics amongst its users must be still designed and the external services to integrate are yet to be determined. These points will be clarified after the completion of the user research activity, carried out by Net7 under task 3.1. This user research activities and outcomes will be fully detailed in the deliverable D3.1 due in M18 (June 2022): for the sake of readability, the following

² See <https://www.operas-eu.org/services/>

chapter presents a short overview of the main user research process that is ongoing in task 3.1.

III. User research process in VERA

In preparation for the definition of VERA specifications, a user research was carried out by Net7 under task 3.1 of WP3. This user research activities and outcomes will be fully detailed in D3.1 due in Month 18 (June 2022). However, for the sake of readability, the following section presents a short overview of the main user research process.

User Research Scope

In order to gain a better understanding of VERA users, a comprehensive user research phase was planned and conducted under the guidance of Net7. The specific aim of user research related to investigating goals, needs and issues target users might have when working on collaborative projects, particularly in the field of SSH. By analyzing gathered user insights, user research artifacts can be created to evaluate features and guide the design phase. To become familiarized with the citizen science landscape and the work being done by the pilots, an exploratory research phase was conducted beforehand. This exploratory research included a benchmark of citizen science platforms and tools, and a digital ethnography³, borrowing anthropological practice, to observe interactions online, to explore active citizen science communities online. Both this initial research and successive user interviews will be fully covered in D3.1.

Interview Sample

In terms of the interview sample, two types of users were defined as targets for conducting interviews: Researchers and Non-Researchers. In both targets, the term “researcher” simply referred to whether or not the user works as a professional/academic researcher. These two categories served to get an overview of user sampling and to create two distinct interview guides.

Within the umbrella of the “non-researcher” category, there were in fact five sub-targets: citizens, NGOs, journalists, artists, and policy makers. Assignment to these sub-targets was based on profession and, in the case of citizens, what kind of role they generally assume during participatory research projects.

In total, 21 users were interviewed (9 researchers, 4 citizens, 3 NGOs, 2 journalists, 2 artists, 1 policy maker).

³ A complete definition of this concept may be found in “Digital Ethnography: Principles and Practice”, Pink S. et al, SAGE, 2015: “*Digital Ethnography outlines an approach to doing ethnography in a contemporary world. It invites researchers to consider how we live and research in a digital, material and sensory environment. This is not a static world or environment. Rather, it is one in which we need to know how to research in it as it develops and changes. Digital Ethnography also explores the consequences of the presence of digital media in shaping the techniques and processes through which we practice ethnography, and accounts for how the digital, methodological, practical and theoretical dimensions of ethnographic research are increasingly intertwined.*”

Interview Recruiting

Using the network of pilot projects and COESO collaborators, 32 people were contacted for interviews. Interviews took place using Zoom and lasted between 1-1.5 hrs on average. Each participant received a consent form before each interview to allow for recording video and audio of the interviews.

Analysis Methodology

Interview recordings were anonymized and safely stored locally. Intelligent transcription was used as a method to aid in note-taking and analysis. Using Airtable, quotes from each section of the interview were progressively coded to allow for thematic concepts to emerge. With these thematic concepts, quotes were then clustered into the following eight overarching themes: Goals, Needs, Problems, Project Cycles, Tools, Data, Community, and Terminology. For a full description of the coding process and resulting themes, see D3.1.

Principal Insights

The results of the user research analysis provided important insights into the goals, needs and pain points people have when collaborating on citizen science projects. In terms of goals, a desire for more public engagement and awareness emerged as a top priority, while creating a shared language to enable collaboration as well as public outreach and project manager roles were highlighted as being core needs for a successful project. As for issues, it is apparent that communication between the academic world and the public is most problematic.

User Research Outcomes

Directly drawing from the user research insights, personas and scenarios were then created to represent the findings of the user research. Personas, fictional representations of target users, are useful for creating empathy between designers and the people who will eventually use the platform. The resulting scenarios, on the other hand, narrate the personas' experience with the platform, and how it fulfills their needs and goals. Five personas, with accompanying scenarios, contextualize the analysis results and allow for the definition of potential design directions the VERA platform can take. Although they will be continuously updated as deemed necessary, these personas and use case scenarios provide a way to make sure VERA responds to our user's goals, needs and pain points as the design phase progresses.

From Research to Design

With the user research phase complete, WP3 moves on to the design of the VERA platform. Through the creation of user stories, we will decide upon core functionalities and sections of the platform. Following the prioritization of these user stories, work can begin on the information architecture and first wireframes. After testing these wireframes with potential users, the team will build interactive prototypes to define the overall look and feel of the platform.

IV. VERA: main functionalities

VERA has to be seen as a “Hub” that interconnects different stakeholders through collaborative services and that engages them in the development of specific Citizen Science SSH related projects.

VERA also aims at being an open architecture, with APIs that easily allow over time the integration of external services or new modules, to extend its features and to remain a live and evolving platform.

In particular, the selection of main tools and modules to be integrated in VERA will be the result of the user research that is being finalized during the period of submission of this deliverable and specific co-design activities that will be performed in the upcoming months and that will address the VERA end users. As previously mentioned, the full details of the user research activity will be described in D3.1.

VERA Hub

Designed with the aim of facilitating:

- Recruiting
- Matching
- Communicating
- Sharing
- Debating
- Training
- Funding

Project Dashboard

This section will be designed with the aim of providing a collaborative environment for projects, therefore it has to provide the functionalities to favour:

- Communicating
- Storing
- Sharing
- Planning
- Debating
- Working (collaboratively)
- Adding/Removing tools

Personal Workspace

This section will be the workspace for users, the main functionalities that this should have are meant to allow them:

- Communicating
- Sharing
- Working (independently)
- Adding/Removing tools

Profile

The profile section will be designed to provide the following functionalities:

- Updating personal information
- Checking feedback/notifications
- Integrating accounts
- Managing tools

V. VERA architecture

From a technical viewpoint, the main functionalities of VERA, described in the previous chapter, find expression in the following diagram, taken from the project proposal.

Figure 1 - VERA application components

VERA in fact focuses on **projects** and must provide intuitive and powerful functionalities that allow users to create and manage their citizen science initiatives.

Users must be able to easily find other people to involve in their projects: the **matching service** represents an answer to this need, allowing the discovery of other persons within VERA, by using the descriptions provided in their profiles. As will be explained in chapter VII, the matching service can also integrate with the OPERAS' service GoTriple, to extend the research of engaged stakeholders externally to VERA, most notably to researchers whose presence is mandatory in a COESO citizen science project.

Paramount for carrying out a project is to ensure an effective communication amongst participants but also with the SSH and citizen science communities at large: the **messaging system**, to be developed for VERA, but reusable in the OPERAS ecosystem, will allow the fulfillment of this requirement.

In order to ease the technical integration with the external tools, used for the management of the VERA citizen science projects, a generic and extensible **integration layer** must be put in place. Designed according to the SOA (Service Oriented Architecture) principles, it will enable third party applications and internal modules to interact and exchange data in an asynchronous fashion, using web service endpoints.

The internal business logic of VERA will be hidden to the front-end and simply exposed to it as web-based APIs managed by the **mediator** service.

Finally, the **VERA Widget** can be seen as a simplified and specialized front-end of VERA. It consists of an HTML code snippet, easy to integrate on external websites (for example on a Wordpress blog), that provides up-to-date information about a specific VERA citizen science project.

From a software architecture viewpoint VERA is a “typical” multi-layered web application, with:

- the front-end layer: it consists of two interactive web applications, that is the dashboard and the VERA Widget, that will be developed in JavaScript technologies
- the back-end layer, where the main business logic of VERA is actually implemented. It also includes the integration logic that allows the interactions with the front-end apps and external services
- the data layer, where data is actually stored.

VERA will be strongly interconnected with multiple application services, either available in the OPERAS ecosystem (see chapter VII. VERA Integration) or from external parties.

Figure 2 - VERA's software architecture

While the main technical details are provided in the chapters that follow, we present here VERA's data model, that is the main “data entities” around which the functionalities of the platform will be built. A high-level view of the model is presented in the diagram below.

Figure 3 - VERA's data model

The model is relatively simple since, as said, the main collaboration activities of a project will happen “elsewhere”, on the external services federated/integrated with VERA.

To use VERA, users must register to the platform: as a first step they must sign up (or authenticate if already registered) on the OPERAS ID service and then they will have to fill up their profiles on VERA. Profile data will be stored in the **User** entity of the VERA database.

In order to simplify this onboarding phase, we will allow to automatically import profile information from a certain number of professional platforms used by the SSH community, including GoTriple, ORCID and LinkedIn.

It is fundamental that users can describe their interests and skills in a quite complete fashion, in order to enable matchmaking with the needs of the projects. We assume therefore that users will complete the registration not only with a textual description but also specifying, by using a classification system, the disciplines and the topics they are interested in and the specializations that they can bring to a citizen science project.

These multiple classifications must be captured in the most precise way, without at the same time making the registration process tedious and cumbersome for the user. For this reason all this information will be proposed by using pre-configured taxonomies: the user will specify them by selecting voices from a list and receiving suggestions through autocomplete. These taxonomies will be the same used for classifying projects (see below).

Users can participate in one or more projects, whose data will be maintained in the **Project** entity of the VERA database. In each one of them they can assume a specific role, including:

- *coordinator-researcher*, in case the project manager is also a researcher
- *coordinator*, for the project manager
- *lead-researcher*: related to the previous case, if the project is not led by a researcher, there must be at least one who assumes the role of scientific coordinator
- *participant*, which is the most generic role for those who join the project
- *follower*, for those who would like to stay informed about the evolution of a project but don't want to actively participate in it.

This is just a preliminary list of the possible roles users can assume in a project: it can be expanded or modified in the course of COESO to better satisfy the real needs of users.

Projects must be properly described, in order to attract the interest of people: therefore they will have both textual descriptions (title, shortDescription, fullDescription), images and documents attached and also a classification done by using either specialized vocabularies for SSH, e.g. those developed in the TRIPLE project (see chapter VII), or other more general-use ontologies (e.g. Wikidata).

The coordinator must also specify the specializations that are needed for the project, in order to simplify the matchmaking with the registered users.

VERA should guide coordinators in the creation of projects, so suggestions of a workflow to follow may be provided to them. Therefore projects will be associated with phases, from the initial idea to the moment in which they become fully operational.

One of the possible integrations with OPERAS services is with the Crowdfunding service. This way a citizen science project managed through VERA can optionally find a way to sustain itself through this alternative funding solution.

The **ExternalConnector** entity enables the use of the external services in a project, also allowing updates to be notified back to the VERA dashboard.

These notifications, together with manual updates on the state of the project provided by the coordinator or other participants, can be stored in the **Post** entity: the VERA dashboard will show the most recent project updates by retrieving data from this database table.

MessagingSpace will be used to associate to a project the “spaces” on the VERA messaging

service. We expect to automatically create two spaces for each project, a private one, available only to registered participants and to be used for management and coordination purposes, and a public one, where more generic exchanges about the progress of the project might happen.

Finally, how to deal with **multilingualism in VERA** hasn't been assessed yet: in any case the implementation must be ready to manage textual data in multiple languages in the same entity of the data model, with a main language and, if needed, an English translation.

VI. Technologies

The choice of technologies for the implementation of VERA has been guided by several factors.

First, VERA is a typical multilayered web application, therefore one of the most common and solid architectures for this kind of implementation has been chosen. It consists of an interactive JavaScript front-end app (actually two apps, if we also consider, together with the dashboard, the VERA widget) and a “headless” back-end, developed in PHP. These two layers interact through web services.

These technologies have been used in several implementations of OPERAS services. GoTriple is in fact developed with exactly the same paradigm and also the current prototype of the Publishing Service Portal, Pathfinder, has been implemented in PHP and JavaScript.

In detail, for VERA the front-end will be developed in TypeScript, a superset of the JavaScript programming language, by using the Angular framework. They are both high-quality open source technologies, used in many mission critical projects worldwide. TypeScript in fact has been created by Microsoft with the intent of making development in JavaScript more robust, resilient to bugs and effective from a productivity viewpoint, while Angular is a front-end web application framework developed by Google and used for its services.

The back-end will be based on the Laravel PHP framework, a technology which is quickly gaining a large adoption, thanks to its expressivity and completeness, which significantly lower development time. Laravel is particularly suitable for developing functionalities which are exposed through web services and in application integration scenarios, the latter thanks to the support of asynchronous communication based on queues. It also supports unit tests out of the box and it provides high-security features.

Both Angular and Laravel are technologies in which Net7 has a deep expertise: they are in fact the basis of the current services for researchers proposed by the company, that is the web annotation service *Pundit* (<https://thepund.it/>) and the *Muruca* (<https://www.muruca.org/>) platform, for implementing and publishing open scholarly editions. Moreover they are well-known by web developers⁴, a fact that helps the long term maintenance of the VERA platform.

For the data layer it was decided to follow a polyglot persistence approach, in which a variety of

⁴ According to the statistics provided by the “2020 State of JS” website, TypeScript is adopted by 78% of developers and Angular by 56% (see <https://2020.stateofjs.com>). Laravel on the other hand is used by 67% of PHP developers according to the estimates provided in “The State of Developer Ecosystem 2021” (see <https://www.jetbrains.com/lp/devecosystem-2021/php/>).

data storage technologies is used for different kinds of data. In particular the main primary data source is managed on the MariaDB relational database, while Elasticsearch will be used for facilitating text search and, especially, for implementing the matchmaking service: these two software products are both common choices in OPERAS implementations (e.g. they are used in GoTriple).

The matchmaking service in VERA will aim at finding the best possible candidates for a specific project by considering:

- the classification of the project on the one hand and the skills and interests of the users on the other. For what has been already said, they will be both codified by using a common taxonomy system
- the textual descriptions, provided both for presenting the project and for the profile of the users.

The use of Elasticsearch will allow matchmaking by using a mix of these two approaches: the former can be more precise when there is an exact match between the categories chosen for the classification of the project and the interests of the user. This is not expected to happen very often, therefore, we will privilege another matching logic, based on similarities found by analyzing the textual descriptions of projects and user profiles, which might guarantee more effective results.

In particular one solution that will be experimented in the project is the use of semantic vector search strategies, which should be particularly accurate in determining logical similarities amongst textual descriptions. Semantic vector search allows capturing not merely the single occurrence of a word but also the context in which it appears.

This possibility can be illustrated with the following example: imagine that in VERA there is a project focused on analyzing how the COVID 19 pandemic has affected the lives of rock musicians; on the other hand, imagine that in the platform there is the profile of an archeologist specialized in rock art. Albeit the word “rock” appears in both descriptions, it is evident that there shouldn’t be a match, since the scopes are totally different. On the contrary, professors of modern music theory might be the perfect persons to be involved, even if the word “rock” isn’t mentioned in their profiles.

From a theoretical viewpoint, the semantic vector search technique consists of an application of the distributional semantic principle, introduced by J. R. Firth and best described by the well-known motto “You shall know a word by the company it keeps”. This expresses the idea that the meaning of words is also dependent on the context in which they are used. Technically speaking, it is implemented by using word embedding algorithms, which allow to codify words in the context in which they appear as numeric vectors. These vectors are geometrically close to each other if the semantic of the corresponding words is also similar.

This feature is available in the open source version of Elasticsearch, that we propose to use through the Elastiknn plug-in (<https://elastiknn.com>).

Finally, for implementing the messaging service, the use of the Mattermost⁵ open source platform will be considered. It is the technology used at Huma-Num to implement the messaging system for various research projects, including COESO, therefore it is very familiar amongst the context

⁵ <https://mattermost.com/>

of OPERAS.

Mattermost has a rich set of APIs that allow to completely control the platform, simplifying therefore the integration with VERA. Its workspaces and communication channels might be accessed through the Mattermost apps, available for desktop and mobile operating systems, or by using a standard web browser. Also, again through APIs, it is possible to integrate a messaging channel on a web site: this way we can directly implement communication functionalities, in the likes of a forum or a chat, directly on the VERA website.

We aim to integrate Mattermost with the OPERAS ID authentication service and to make it reusable for every OPERAS initiative, not only COESO. Automatically every citizen science project defined in COESO will have dedicated channels, where, again through APIs, participants will be automatically registered.

VII. VERA integration

We present in this section the strategies and some technical details regarding VERA integration with other services, in particular with those of OPERAS and in particular with GoTriple, the discovery platform in the course of development in the TRIPLE EU research project (<https://project.gotriple.eu/>).

VERA has been designed in respect of the “valorisation principle”, to reuse the existing (and under development) functionalities of OPERAS services but also to make some of its own features ready to be used in the OPERAS ecosystem.

The integration with EU-Citizen.Science, a project in which COESO partner Ibercivis is involved, deserves special attention: the possible strategy to integrate VERA with it is described in this chapter.

Finally, it is important to point out that in this document we do not cover the exact number and type of external services for carrying out the work on the citizen science projects. Their identification is in fact still an on-going process, linked to the user analysis of task 3.1, done in collaboration with the COESO pilots of WP2.

VERA in the context of OPERAS

We present here the functionalities of OPERAS’ services that VERA will integrate with.

For user registration and authentication the **OPERAS ID service**, under development in the course of the TRIPLE project, will be used. Integrating this service with VERA makes perfect sense, since it is expected that a significant part of its user base might coincide with that of other OPERAS services, in particular of GoTriple.

The purpose of the service is to represent a central authentication point and not a full profile management service. Therefore only a few personal data of the user (name, surname and email) will be maintained in it. The great added value of the service is also the proxy authentication functionality, that allows users to register and subsequently authenticate with several, widely

used identity management systems, employed both in the context of research (e.g. ORCID, EduGain, LinkedIn and soon EGI AAI Check-In Account) and for daily/personal use (Google, Twitter).

By using this service in every OPERAS implementation, it becomes possible to maintain a central and unique repository of users, allowing also single sign-on scenarios amongst different OPERAS services: for example, researchers who need to use both GoTriple and VERA at the same time will only have to authenticate once.

It is important to point out that OPERAS ID won't be a user profile management system. Every OPERAS service might in fact need a different data schema to describe users: for example VERA will be focused on citizen science and therefore it is unnecessary to ask users to provide detailed information regarding their research careers.

For what has been just said, users, after having registered on OPERAS ID, will fill in all the required profile information in the respective OPERAS services. For example, the user journey for user onboarding that will happen for VERA is depicted in the diagram that follows.

Figure 4 - User registration in VERA with the use of OPERAS ID

OPERAS ID is being implemented by refactoring the existing Huma-Num ID service, whose main interface is shown in the image below.

Log in with an external account ⓘ

Reset my password

HN Login with HumanID ?

Your first visit on Huma-Num ?

HN Create a Huma-Num account

eduGAIN Log in with eduGAIN

ORCID Login with ORCID

HAL Log in with HAL account

LinkedIn Log in with LinkedIn

Twitter Log in with Twitter

Google Log in with Google

Figure 5 - Huma-Num ID service

VERA will reuse multiple functionalities developed in the course of the TRIPLE project. The fact that GoTriple has a multilayered architecture, with several specialized applicative services, helps the integration of its functionalities in the OPERAS world.

The main goal of TRIPLE is to implement a discovery platform for the SSH domain: the service revolves around a repository with data about publications, datasets, projects and researcher profiles that are automatically imported, normalized and semantically enriched from multiple web sources. The repository is implemented with the Elasticsearch server whose “documents” are searchable and retrievable through APIs. These **TRIPLE APIs** have been designed to implement the search features of the front-end of the GoTriple platform but might be reused by other applications as well. In particular in VERA we might exploit the search APIs to simplify the identification of researchers to involve in a citizen science project.

For this purpose other specific TRIPLE APIs could be used, that is, those of the Recommender System. The latter is one of the Innovative Services of TRIPLE which allows the suggestion of “related content” given an “example” provided as input. In GoTriple, this service suggests similar publications of an article presented in its landing page and possible content of interest for a user, given his/her reading history. The Recommender is a quite agnostic technology regarding the typology of suggestions to provide: in particular as a next step, in TRIPLE it will be used to provide recommendations regarding projects and, especially, researchers. The latter option is of course very interesting for VERA. Suggestions in fact might be driven by generic textual descriptions: this way we might implement in VERA an automatic and targeted recommendation of researchers to contact given the description of a citizen science project.

Also, it is worth to mention that TRIPLE has integrated - again as an Innovative Service - the eTranslation API⁶ for the automatic translation in English of textual content (e.g. articles’

⁶ eTranslation is a Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) whose goal is to help European and national public administrations to exchange information across language barriers in the EU, by providing machine

abstracts, projects' descriptions,...), when the version in this language is not available. We might think of exploiting this feature as a TRIPLE API, in order to guarantee that an English translation for the descriptive parts of a VERA project is always available.

VERA might also exploit the **TRIPLE Classification System**, which consists of 27 categories to describe the main SSH disciplines and a multilingual thesaurus of 2.500 keywords.

The 27 disciplines classification exploits the result of the MORESS (Mapping of Research in European Social Sciences and Humanities) research project, a EU-funded initiative that ran from 2003 to 2005 and was coordinated by the European University Association (EUA). These categories, which proposed an effective classification for SSH disciplines, were one of its outcomes.

The TRIPLE thesaurus on the other hand was created by extracting a subset of the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH) related to the SSH domain and aptly translated in the nine languages TRIPLE supports in a semi-automatic way.

Another API that GoTriple might be exposed to VERA is that of the **TRIPLE Automatic Classification and Annotation service**, which, given the abstract of the citizen science initiative, returns the possible categories/disciplines and the keywords from the TRIPLE thesaurus that can be associated to the project. This way it would be possible in VERA to provide a suggestion system for helping coordinators to better classify their projects: this automatic classification won't be mandatory and changes, integrations or merely cancellations will be left to the responsibility of the coordinators.

The **OPERAS Crowdfunding service**, in the course of activation, will be exploitable for VERA's citizen science initiatives, as an alternative and efficient way to provide the economic opportunities for implementing a project. The exact details of this integration are still to be assessed (e.g. in particular if there will be a certain degree of automatization or simply an identified workflow to follow, with tutorials to read and specific contact points to get in touch with).

In COESO we won't simply integrate OPERAS' services functionalities in VERA but we will also create new tools and datasets that can be valorized and become common, reusable features of the OPERAS ecosystem.

First of all, all **COESO projects** will be automatically imported in GoTriple and made searchable through this discovery platform.

COESO will make available its **Messaging System** for OPERAS, integrated with OPERAS ID for authentication and in which dedicated workspaces will be devoted to every single OPERAS service (e.g. one workspace for COESO/VERA, one for TRIPLE, etc.). Each workspace/OPERAS service might have assigned one or more communication channels, with different visibility and privacy rules (e.g. public, restricted to specific users, private). For example in VERA we might have one or more channels automatically created for each citizen science project, e.g. a private one accessible only to the members of the project, a public channel open to the public.

As said, the technology that we plan to use is Mattermost. In particular the technical work that

translation capabilities that enable all Digital Service Infrastructures (DSIs) to be multilingual.

will be carried out for that in COESO includes:

- the installation and configuration of the software platform in the servers available for COESO
- the implementation of an authentication plug-in to support the OPERAS ID service
- the development of a PHP management library to allow the creation of workspaces and channels, their configuration, in particular regarding visibility and privacy, and the subscription (or cancellation) of users to the various channels
- the development of a JavaScript library to ease the integration of communication services based on Mattermost in the front-end of a website.

Finally, also the **search of available funding opportunities for SSH**, implemented in VERA through the integration of the Fund.it service, might become another common functionality of the OPERAS ecosystem. This possibility will be analyzed and, in case, implemented in the following months.

Integration with EU-Citizen.Science

EU-Citizen.Science is an online platform -built under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, grant agreement No. 824580- for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science, by the community, for the community.

The vision for this platform is to serve as a Knowledge Hub, in aid of the mainstreaming of Citizen Science, and build on the growing impact of citizens participating in research across the full range of scientific inquiry. EU-Citizen.Science platform accomplishes these goals by supporting the sharing of knowledge, know-how, and experience between anyone doing or wanting to do Citizen Science. The platform was built by Ibercivis together with the ECSA association⁷. The source code of the EU-Citizen.Science platform was released under EUPL license and is available in Github⁸.

The EU-Citizen.Science platform provides an API⁹ to push and pull projects, resources, training resources, organizations and events.

Thanks to the integration with EU-Citizen.Science, projects and resources in VERA will be automatically pushed to the EU-Citizen.Science platform. In this way, content created under the COESO project will be available under the EU-Citizen.Science platform, facilitating their discovery by the European Citizen Science community.

It has also to be noted that the focus of VERA on SSH Citizen Science projects covers a gap within the Citizen Science European landscape which strongly and usually focuses on Natural Sciences. Therefore the integration of VERA with the EU-Citizen.Science platform will benefit and enrich the latter by feeding projects and resources from the SSH domain.

⁷ <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/>

⁸ https://github.com/Ibercivis/EU-CS_platform

⁹ <https://eu-citizen.science/swagger/>

VIII. Conclusions

The current deliverable, which presented the development and setup of the alpha version of VERA, is a living document that will evolve as long as the platform is implemented and the project activities carried out.

In addition to the main functionalities already depicted in this deliverable, the user research results will provide further inputs for the tools and functionalities to be developed and/or integrated in VERA. The release of a beta version of the platform (Month 24 - December 2022) will represent the evolution of VERA as a collaborative environment, designed **for and with** the user community.

VERA is positioned amongst a constellation of services and tools for the SSH community. Being an OPERAS service and being developed to make it interoperable with the other services of this infrastructure (e.g those provided by the TRIPLE project) as well as with the EU-Citizen.Science platform, paves the way for it to become a powerful tool for the Citizen Science community in SSH.

The accurate user research that has been and will continue being carried out with end users contributes to building an environment within COESO that has what it takes to become *the* reference platform for Citizen Science in SSH in Europe.